

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B433

Date: 3 Mar 2009:

Take Off: 1102:54

Landing: 15:42:09

Flight Time: 4h 39m 15s

Campaign: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies

Operating Area: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	Y
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	Y
6	Core Chem	Doug Anderson	FAAM	N
7	Cloud Physics 1	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	Y
8	Wet Nephelometer / PSAP	Simon Osbourne	FAAM	Y/N
9	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	N
10	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester University	N
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Xchat	No log available
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump / filter info included on Flight Summary page
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
Wet Neph	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

no data on BADC 30 Dec 2009

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B433 10:38:43–15:55:06

GLon_PARA0611, GLat_PARA0610

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies

Date: 03 Feb 2009

B433 (double flight): t/o (Cranfield) 11:00z, land (Exeter) 15:15z

B434: t/o (Exeter) 16:45z, land (Exeter) 20:45z

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Location: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs at a series of altitudes below cloud base (if possible), within and above the cloud, along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign "Radsearch"). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles through it. It is desired that the aircraft flight legs start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so may limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail B433:

- a) Take off & climb to FL100 to transit to operating area at Chilbolton.
- b) When at suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl, or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions. Fly 10min **clear air** leg in vicinity of Chilbolton.
- c) Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL330 or to above cloud top, whichever is lower.
- d) Fly a series of 40-60km level flight legs along the azimuth scanned by the radar at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Ideally, just above cloud base, throughout the cloud, just below and just above cloud top. Duration of each leg ~10 minutes. Legs should extend over Chilbolton. During incloud legs AMS should sample off CVI inlet unless tip iced up (but sample off Rosemount inlet out of cloud). Filters to be exposed on out of cloud legs only.
- e) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest or one that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern.
- f) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- g) Repeat items d) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.
- h) End with below-cloud clear air aerosol leg (10 min) if possible, before recovering to destination airfield.

Sortie Detail B434:

As above except for takeoff and transit from Exeter airfield onto Chilbolton Radial to begin science, landing back at Exeter.

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Clouds – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 um), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 um using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, CAPS and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer, CR2
- GPS, GIN, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud/Aerosol Physics/Chemistry

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- 2DS, CAPS and FSSP – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, SMPS/WCPC (- to sample off Rosemount inlet)
- Filters

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies:
Flight Number: B433, 3rd March 2009 (Take-off 11:02z, landing 15:42z at Exeter)
Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims & operating area: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Weather conditions: During March 2, a number of low pressure systems aligned along a WSW-ENE axis through Iceland joined together to form an area of low pressure that was centred over Iceland by midnight (still extending beyond the island to the NE and SW; Fig 1 below). This region of low pressure spawned a number of frontal systems which moved across the UK during March 2nd and 3rd. During March 2nd, a system comprising of a warm front and two cold fronts moved slowly across the British Isles from the west. By midnight (Fig 1) it covered the southern half of England, and by 6am on the 3rd, was positioned across the SE of the country, the cold front lying in line from the north coast of Devon and Cornwall to the Wash. The timing of these fronts was such that they crossed through the operational (Chilbolton) area early in the morning before it was possible to take off from Cranfield. In addition they were forecasted (eg by the UK 4km model) to not be very active and indeed they were seen not produce a lot of precipitation or an extended period of deep cloud. However a wave had been predicted to develop along the trailing tail of the cold front out to the SW which was forecasted to generate the return of a section of the front northeastwards (now as a warm front) which by midday was expected to be over the south western regions (Fig 2 - actual). This was forecasted to be a much more active feature generating significant precipitation and an extended period of deep cloud cover over southern UK at least until 9pm. Based on this it was decided to carry out a double flight on March 3rd, the first B433 set to measure the arrival of the upper level cloud associated with the approaching warm front together with a chance to measure the aerosol input at lower levels in clear air. Later into the flight the cloud was expected to deepen, with cloud bases extending down to mid and lower levels. In order to maximise the available flight crew hours, an initial takeoff at 11:00z for a 4.25 hour flight was planned to be followed by a refuelling stop at Exeter. This allowed for a second flight to occur to measure the main part of the front as it crossed through the operational area during early evening, before the aircraft landed away at Exeter for an overnight stop.

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 03 Mar 2009 0000 UTC

Fig 3 : IR satellite picture 00:00z 030309

EIEB51 MSG 108 micron Infrared Image 03 Mar 2009 1200 UTC

Fig 4 : IR satellite picture 12:00z 030309

The actual synoptic situation during the day on March 3rd saw another cold front approach the British Isles from the NW (Fig 2 above), and a new centre of low pressure formed at the apex of the wave to the SW of the UK. By late afternoon on the 3rd this low had tracked NE-wards to be over North Wales (centred on Anglesey – Fig 7) and this linked the remains of the cold front in the wave with the final cold front from the NW.

Figs 5, 6 and 7: (left to right) showing the synoptic situation at 12:00z, 14:00z and 17:00z respectively

As forecasted this evolving system was much more active than the initial fronts had been, generating heavy precipitation (see rainfall radar figures 8, 9 and 10 below for 11:15z, 13:15z and 15:15z respectively), high winds and thick cloud (see fig 4 above) at all levels throughout the troposphere. The cloud was now forecasted to remain over southern England (and the Chilbolton area) for the rest of the afternoon and evening and into the

next day, until the centre of low pressure had moved northwards (north of Scotland) and the trailing cold front had passed fully across the country by first light on March 4th.

Figs 8, 9 and 10: (left to right) showing rainfall over the UK observed at 11:15z, 13:15z and 15:15z respectively

Summary of the flight: Prior to and following take-off there were problems with the Horace logging system which persisted throughout the transit to the operational area. Even in the absence of a working 35GHz radar at Chilbolton, the radar station reported (from RHI scans) cloud top (CT) at 8km (26.2kft) and a sloping cloud base (CB) from 6km (20kft) overhead Chilbolton (CH) to 4.5km (14.8kft) at 100km range to the west. They also reported CB to be descending, consistent with the approaching warm frontal surface. On the approach to Boscombe Down airfield (in order to get to low level to carry out aerosol measurement legs) locally CT was encountered at FL70. At FL60 (810mbar, -5.76°C) CPI reported loads of liquid water, particularly in the form of large liquid precipitation drops. During the descent in the approach to Boscombe, a local CB was encountered at FL50 (840mbar, -1.68°C) but CB was extremely variable/inhomogeneous, and the aircraft remained in and out of cloud down to at least 2000ft (altimeter on QFE 991). Because of the presence of low cloud, a below cloud aerosol leg was not possible and following a missed approach to Boscombe airfield it was decided to carry out a profile ascent (P3) from 50ft up to and through the mid level cloud to FL270 above CT.

During P3, a low level CB was encountered at around 2200ft (on QFE 991, 924mbar/2.5kft, 3.2°C), while the freezing level was around 3500ft (869mbar/4.1kft, -0.2°C). CT was encountered flying outbound from CH at FL60 (811mbar -3.7°C). In this intermediate cloud free layer, PCASP was seeing just 2-6 cm⁻³ while the CPC saw around 60 cm⁻³. The CB of the mid/upper cloud was seen at around FL142 (588mbar, -19.0°C). After turning at the SW end of the CH radial, the 1st CT was encountered inbound at around FL240 (391mbar, -38.9°C), as the aircraft turned again to complete the profile at the SW end of the CH radial. There was more cirrus above. Chilbolton now reported CT at 8km+ and CB ~6km overhead the radar as the front continued its eastward progress. The profile broke through the main CT at FL267 locally (348mbar, -46.2°C). At FL270 (344mbar, -46.9°C) the plane immediately started a profile (P4) back down to an incloud level, and turned to return inbound to CH. At FL230 (408mbar, -37.2°C) the first SLR R1 was started. Chilbolton report the same high cloud situation but with showers out to the west at a range of 90-95km, falling ~2km. During R1 core cloud reported “small ice” but

CPI was seeing bullet rosettes (BR) and short stubby columns although 2DS and CIP (CAPS) did not see the BRs. R1 proceeded through some open pockets of cloud free air, but there was always more Ci above. Even above the local CT, 200µm particles were observed. Overhead Chilbolton inbound, some smaller more pristine particles were observed. In the turn the aircraft was in and out of cloud and saw some bigger and smaller particles alternately. After passing CH outbound a profile (P5) down to FL210 was carried out. PI Choularton (TWC) reported the leading edge of the precipitation to now lie on a line from Bristol to Exeter (12:26z).

A series of SLR legs outbound and inbound at descending levels was then undertaken down to FL60. SLRs were linked by profile descents in the turn at the SW end of the legs and just after passing CH outbound at the NE end. Runs R2, R3, R4, R5, R6, R7, R8, R9, R10 and R11 were carried out at flight levels; FL210, FL190, FL170, FL150, FL130, FL110, FL100, FL90, FL70 and FL60 respectively, and linked by profile descents P6, P7, P8, P9, P10, P11, P12, P13 and P14. Because of the time taken to profile down to the next level outbound (after passing CH) the length of outbound SLRs is shorter although flying into wind compensates somewhat by slowing the aircraft down (relative to ground). The properties of these runs are summarised in the table 1 below. Finally, to cover the melting layer within the remaining time available, after turning during R11 and passing CH outbound, a saw tooth profile leg was undertaken to get back to Exeter for refuelling. Profiles P15.1, P15.2, P15.3, P15.4 and P16 were undertaken between FL60, 3kft, FL50, 2.5kft, FL50 and FL40. R13 was then carried out at FL40 on the approach to Exeter. The aircraft landed at Exeter at 15:41z in a strong crosswind and heavy rain.

Table 1 – descending SLRs

P # u/d Run #	in/out bound (I /O)	Flight level	Run Pressure (mbar)	Temp start/end SLR(°C)	Comments/observations
P5 d R2	O	FL210	445	-32.5 -32.2	Core cloud (CC) reported relatively large ice crystals, habits as at higher altitude but bigger. CPI reported more aggregates and a few columns. The mode size (CPI) increased along run to be ~250µm
P6 d R3	I	FL190	484	-28.5 -28.2	During P6 2DC mode as large as 600µm generally 400µm, while CPI mode was ~300µm. Flight Man reported loss of turb probe attack angle (iced up prob ~11:50z). CPI reported CAPS pitot tube iced up at start R3. Chilbolton reports thicker cloud to east, and front now at 70km range (from CH) CC - area of smaller ice approaching CH. CPI reports increase in mean size half way to Exeter. CH reports Ci CT ~9km (29.5kft) CT 5.5km (18kft) CB 4.5km at 50km range, 2km at 100km range (and strong ppt)
P7 d R4	O	FL170	525	-24.4	At end P7 CPI – mode diameter inc 500-600µm as we go west, CC agrees. CPI

R4				-23.7	reports inc small ice particles – effect inlet shattering? CC agrees, very large crystals. Both CC/CPI seeing water? CC - small round stuff, CPI - some in focus drops
P8 d R5	I	FL150	570	-19.6 -19.7	Possible water again, CPI not so much ice. Crystal diameter increasing as altitude of runs decreases. Bumpy as we go E CH reports Ci at 9km seeding CTs at 6.6km (21.3kft) CB now at 4km (40km range) 2km (50km range) and ppt at 65km ahead of main ppt. Bright sunshine in turn east of CH (photos) Captain wind 225°/40kts (turb 224°/27m/s) CH – rapid inc frontal activity 40km range
P9 d R6	O	FL130	617	-15.3 -15.1	R6 CC/CPI report definite liquid water half distance along radial
P10 d R7	I	FL110	668	-11.4 -10.8	CH CB now 4.5km (14.8kft) over CH and 2.2km (7.2kft) at 20-30km, ppt at 40km. Aircraft – huge amount ppt except OH CH. In turn PCASP 20-30 cm ⁻³ CAS 2 cm ⁻³ CPC 160 cm ⁻³ , CCN50 cm ⁻³ (0.2%) AMS low SO ₄ ²⁻ , Org (see fig 11 below re water along radial as fn(longitude))
P11 d R8	O	FL100	695	-9.1 -8.8	Bumpy now right after start R8 (8-10km range), some water but ice dominated CH report CB now 3km overhead, pp at 18km range (west) Captain 232°/50kts (turb 229°/29m/s)
P12 d R9	I	FL90	723	-7.3 -7.7	CC sees snow & liquid water (2DC 150µm doughnuts) but CPI says 50µm not water but ice fragments. CH (3GHz radar) reports ppt at CH at 1km 2DC seeing 30 litre ⁻¹ FSSP 2-3 cm ⁻³ CAS 2-3 cm ⁻³ but CDP noisy. CPI sees ppt directly over CH
P13 d R10	O	FL70	781	-4.2 -3.5	pocket liquid water 200m wide during P13 CH reports high cloud thinning out, CT (of NiSt) sloping up away from CH 3km at 30km 4km at 70km. CC/CPI seeing columns + hint of liquid. 2/3 of outbound leg. 3mm snowflakes previously seen above – gone. Alternately seeing columns dominating with liquid - and then not CH reports supercooled drops 14-15kft OH Shorter colums seen end of run, but 2DS seeing monster blobs 1mm across. Captain – wind 226°/52kts (turb probe 219°/30m/s)
P14 d R11	I	FL60	810	-2.2 -2.3	Turbulence probe now de-iced/working CDP sees “pointy” spectra in ice but now smooth spectra in water cloud. Couple pockets supercooled water, then all ice

Table 2 – final sawtooth profiles on leg inbound to Exeter

P #	u/d	u/d – up/down	Starting level	Pressure (mbar)	Temp start(°C)	Comments/observations
P15.1	d	d	FL60	811	-2.3	
P15.2	u	u	3kft	882	+0.8	
P15.3	d	d	FL50	844	-1.0	
P15.4	u	u	2.5kft	918	+3.2	
R12	SLR	SLR	FL50	845	-0.85	
P16	d	d	FL50	845	-0.38	
R13	SLR	SLR	FL40	872	1.0	Approach to Exeter

Notes on instrumentation:

The main problems were associated with the Core Data logging system, Horace, at the start of the flight (data from 11:25z). The turbulence probe attack parameter was affected by icing from about 11:50z onwards until near the end and the CAPS pitot tube also froze up during the flight (For a full list of other instrumentation functionality see flight log)

Mission Scientist's Log [APPRAISE-CLOUDS]

Flight No B.....433a Date ..03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page ...1 of ...10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts	
	(KNB bin = +52s)				Starting from Mission 2/3 seat today.....	
10:48.56	KNB	10:51.26			Engine Start 4-1	
10.51.49	"				Power Change Over	
10.56.36	"				Taxi (- some scattered low level blue sky)	
11.03.16	"				Rolling	
11.03.45	"				T/O	
		~1500ft			CB	
* * *					MORACE problems - difficult to summarise.... *	
				Chilbolton:-	Multiple layers cloud - Chilbolton report:-	
					CB 500m	
					Intermittent Showers	
					RHI - CT ~ 8000m + (26.2kt)	
					↓ CB ~ 6000m OH CT (20kt)	
					To 4500m (14.8kt)	
					at 100km range	
x	11.23.52	PI Snt	FL100		Run transit level - No Morace data	
✓	11.24.45	PI	8.3kt	178	51°48'/1°36'	741mb -8.05°/-10.47° 15m/s/209°
x	11.25.43	PI	~7000			CT - getting bumpy - Morace freeze up
✓	11.27.05	PI Int	6000ft	206	51°42'/1°36'	ATC hold on Boscombe approach [-5.76°/-2.15°C
						loads LWC here - CPI
						810mb
						21m/s/211°
						ZDS affine:-
						large liquid ppt.
✓	11.29.59	PI resume	5.8kt	138	51°30'/1°42'	815mb -3.64°/-1.54°C 16m/s/209°
	11.30.26	PI	5000ft	110	51°30'/1°42'	local CB 840mb, -1.65°/-0.84° 17/218°
						CB is variable - inhomogeneous.

MORACE STATUS
↓

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. ⁴³³ Date 03/03/09 Name K. N. BOWER Page 2 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11.31.23	P1 hdd	4000	107°	51°30'/1°36'	Mainly in cloud, +0.55°/-0.05°C 17m/s/216° 873mb
11.34.13	P2 skt	4000	172°	51°24'/1°30'	(Sfc 200°/17kt gusting) 873mb 0.32°/0.93°
11.35.14	P2	2500ft	172	51°18'/1°24'	(on QFE 991) 901mb/3.1kft 1.95°/2.57° 18m/s/212°
11.35.41	P2 mt	2000ft	172	51°15'/1°24'	920mb/2.6kft 2.9°/3.89° 16m/s/200
11.37.07	-	2000ft	222	51°12'/1°24'	In end out cloud, 920mb/2.6kft 2.9°/3.13° 17m/s/202°
					920mb 2.9°/3.31° 17/202°
11.40.34	P2 res	2000ft	225	51°12'/1°36'	Resume P2 921mb/2.6kft 2.68°/3.44° 19m/s/208°
11.41.27	P2	1500ft	224	51°12'/1°36'	938mb/2.1kft 3.98°/3.76° 18m/s/203°
11.42.14	P2	1000ft	226	51°6'/1°36'	952mb/1.6kft 5.01°/4.37° 18m/s/201°
11.43.04	P2	500ft	223	51°6'/1°42'	971mb/1.1kft 6.45°/5.17° 14m/s/198°
11.43.51	P2E/ P3.3	50ft	228	51°6'/1°42'	989mb/0.6kft 7.88°/5.81° 12m/s/200°
11.44.19	P3	500ft	224	51°6'/1°42'	971mb/1.1kft 6.82°/5.34° 14m/s/190°
11.44.49	P3	1000ft	227	51°6'/1°42'	955mb/1.6kft 5.27°/4.8° 18m/s/203°
11.45.14	P3	2000ft	235	51°6'/1°48'	937mb/2.1kft 3.89°/3.76° 21m/s/208°
11.45.28	P3	2200ft	240	51°6'/1°48'	CB: 924mb/2.5kft 3.22°/2.89° 20m/s/212°
11.46.09	P3	3500ft	264	51°6'/1°48'	869mb/4.1kft -0.21°/1.5°C 20m/s/219.
11.46.09	P3				→ p settings (changed back) - continue P3 up to mid level CT.
11.46.47	P3	5100ft	264	51°6'/1°54'	841mb/5.0kft -1.69°/-0.74° 21m/s/214°
11.47.27	P3	6000ft	262	51°6'/2°0'	811mb/6.0kft -3.73°/-1.32° 19m/s/210°
11.48.17	P3	6.9kft	247	51°6'/2°0'	CT, 783mb/6.9kft -5.55°/-6.75° 22/219°
11.50.42	P3	FL100	244	51°0'/2°12'	(On 1013mb) 693mb -10.34°/-31.8° 20m/s/220
11.54.05	P3	FL142	242	50°54'/2°30'	CBs - very thin CPI some ice -15.93°/-15.78° 568mb 24m/s/224°
11.54.48	P3	FL151	242	50°54'/2°36'	567mb -20.11°/-19.44° 22m/s/227°
11.51.28	P3	FL110	243	51°0'/2°18'	669mb -11.94°/-15.77° 19m/s/225°

PCASP - 2-6, 3, 0
CPI - 60 cm⁻³

CT - 60 after 11.25 no droplets on Mirac

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...433 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 3 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11.55.56	P3	FL165	238	50°54'/2°42'	537mb -22.91°/-22.19°C 25m/s/231°
[SW] 11.56.19	P3	FL169	237	50°54'/2°42'	RMT at SW end 529mb -23.02°/23.59 22/230°
11.58.03	P3	FL190	50	50°54'/2°48'	485mb -27.3°C/-26.19°C 19m/s/224°
11.59.21	P3	FL225	117	50°54'/2°36'	-38.68°/-38.9°C 19m/s/235 456mb
12.01.34	P3	FL250	73	50°54'/2°18'	411mb -36.0°/-37.15°C 19m/s/267°
12.02.54	P3	FL240	292	51°0'/2°18'	1 st CT - more Ci above though -35.83°/39.12° 371 ^{mb}
12.04.09	P3	FL250	240	51°0'/2°24'	375mb, -41.38°/-42.45°C 25m/s/256°
					Chilbolton report (on 255° radial)
					CT 8000m+ (26.2kft)
					CB 6000m (DMH) (19.6kft)
					showers: 2000m on 255 radial (6.6kft)
					at 42-46km range.
12.06.06 FL260	P3	FL260	246	50°54'/2°36'	359mb -44.3°/-45.34°C 28m/s/253°
12.07.20	P3	FL267	245	50°54'/2°42'	low CT. 345mb -46.22°/-44.46° 29/255
12.07.49	P3E/ P4S	FL270	245	50°48'/2°48'	344mb -46.57°/45.12°C 30m/s/261° down to an in-cloud run
[SW] 12.09.06	P4	FL255	3	50°54'/2°54'	367mb, -42.97°/-47.06°C 12m/s/295°
12.09.45	P4	FL246	65	50°54'/2°45'	375mb, -41.02°/-41.15° 17m/s/218°
					MSci 2 reports..... (Stopped on)
12.10.36	P4	FL239	116	50°54'/2°42'	393mb, -39.55°/-39.95° 17m/s/216°
12.11.31	P4/ P1S	FL230	111	50°54'/2°36'	408mb -37.18°/-36.74° 11m/s/215°
					MSci 2 some High Cloud still as before.... but
					showers 40km alt on new one
					now at 90-95 km alt of 2000m clouds
12.13.30					-
12.19.39	R1	FL230			at 01 see over page.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...⁴³³ Date ...03/03/09 Name ...K.N. BOWER Page ...4... of ...10...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Core Awd - Small ice now - but
					CPI → Bullet Rosette + short stubby columns
					with - marks 100-500 (CPI)
					2DS/CIP not seeing BRs !!
					- In and out of ice open pockets here
					- more Ci layers above us.
12.13.36	R1	FL230	70	50°54'/2°18'	409mb -36.26/-37.72 15m/s/261°
					200µm particles now - Above CT locally
[CH] → 12.19.37	R1	FL230	76	51°6'/1°24'	409mb -37.31/-37.27 12m/s/244° OH CH
					Smaller stuff - more pristine than bigger stuff
12.21.32	R1	FL230	131	51°6'/1°6'	in turn - in/out cloud bigger/smaller stuff
[CH] ← 12.24.55	R1E/15S	FL230	252	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH, 409mb -37.14/-37.25°C 29m/s/231
12.26.30					MSi 2 - leading edge Bristol to Ester (TWC)
					- holes/gaps between cloud layers.
12.27.09	15E/12S	FL210	252	51°0'/1°36'	CC - red large ice, some as higher up/larger now
					CIT - more aggs - couple columns
					-32.47°C/-33.03°, 445mb, 30m/s/243°
					MSi 2 - TWC - cloud front clearing CH at ~9pm
					CH - Ci OH - low whips 9000m (29.5kft)
					CB ~ 8500 - (18kft)
					+ low Strato cumulus.
					light showers 16-30 km; 1800m CT.
					Alt St: CB ~ 4500m at 50km range
					(14.8kft) L
					TWC - Mesocyclone mod: N. Strato - reaches CH

~ 3pm this afternoon

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.433 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. Bowee Page 5 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					CI ice getting bigger - made at 250µm
[SW] 12.37.29	R2E/P6S	FL210	253	50°48'/2°42'	445mb, -32.2°/-31.51°, 29m/s/235
12.38.27	P6	FL200	336	50°54'/2°45'	464mb, -29.70°/-29.27°, 13m/s/275
					ZDC max size ~ 600µm mainly 400µm CI ~ 300µm
12.39.26	P6E/R3S	FL190	73°	50°54'/2°45'	484mb, -28.47°/-27.6°, 25m/s/206
				NB * * *	- angle of attack - maybe used over on barb probe 11.50 ish (affects wind direction)
					CI - problem with turbulence possible - cos... CAPS lost Pitot tube recently too.... 237 / 240kts - Captain - so wind ~ 01kts. Angle attack stopped working at ~ 11.50ish
				Report:	CH - thicker cloud → East front at 70 km West - so get into it at end of runs now.
12.48.12	R3				Area of smaller ice - CI →
[CH] 12.49.35	R3	FL190	77	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH, 484mb -27.72°/-28.32 14m/s/236° CI - would like to continue ↓ legs from here on. (increase in mean size half way to Exeter) MSci2 - OH similar 5500m ET (18kft) Ci CT ~ 9000m (29.5kft) 50km out to West, CB gently descent 4500m 75km out EB ~ 2000m 100km ppt out 100km range
[CH] 12.54.52	R3	FL190	264	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH 484mb -28.12°/-28.36° (27m/s/229)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 433 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 6 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12.55.21	R3E/P75	FL190	248	51°6'/1°24'	483mb -28.24/-28.42°C, 27m/s/236°
12.57.29	R3E/R4	FL170	248	51°6'/1°24'	525mb -24.55/-23.46°C 29m/s/227
					made diameter 500-600µm as we go west
					CC - agrees.
					CPI - small ice fragments shattering on inlet
					LW ≡ ⁺
					CC - agrees - really large ice crystals here
					CC/CPI - CC seeing water
					↳ small round looking stuff
					CPI - few in lens obs.
13.08.59	R4	FL170	250	50°48'/2°42'	526mb, -23.27/-23.2° 29m/s/237°
13.11.40	R4E/P8	FL170	116	50°54'/2°36'	526mb, -23.65/-22.83°C 21m/s/228
13.13.32	R5E/R5	FL150	76	50°54'/2°24'	570mb, -19.62/-19.16°C 14m/s/218°
					- Attachment on Tube still iced up
					- possibly water → CC → CPI not so much ice
					φ inc with ↑ Altitude. it seems.
13.20.09	R5	FL150	79	♂	Bumping as going further East
					Chilbolton Ci: C1 9000m (29.5kft)
					seedling mid level ~ 6500m (21.3kft)
					(3kft) ← CB 4000m 40km
					(6.5kft) but 2000m 50km
					part at 65 km range + showers
					ahead of main part..
13.21.19	R5	FL150			ON ON 571mb -19.59/-36.95°C 15m/s/233

[SW]
↻

[CN]
→

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 433 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 7 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
				Answer...	TWC - start to plan re landing times
13.22.44	RS	FL150	64	51°6'/1°12'	turning, 571mb -19.73°/-37.22° 20m/s/200° Bright Sunsets - this end of run - clear sky - photos.... (NB photo time USA eastern -5hrs) 225/40 } Captain 27/ 224° recmd. 230/41 } - still seems OK !! MSci - Chil - Scan rapid inc frontal activity (14.7 AFT) ← 4500m, 35-40km W pass-
13.26.31	R5E/R5	FL150	241	51°6'/1°24'	570mb, -19.67°/-32.74°, 27m/s/225°
13.28.52	R9E/R6	FL150	251	51°6'/1°36'	617mb, -15.27°/-35.6°, 29m/s/229°
13.32.29	R6	FL130	248	51°0'/1°54'	Core Cloud + CPI report liquid water here CPI - "collapsing at water" Report :- TWC - confirm going off back time OK
13.41.45	R6E/P10	FL130	250	50°48'/2°42'	618mb, -15.1°/-15.51°, 30m/s/235°
13.42.51	P10	FL119	8°	50°54'/2°48'	646mb, -13.03°/-12.93°, 12m/s/222°
13.43.56	P10E/R7	FL110	106°	50°54'/2°42'	668mb, -11.39°/-11.0°, 19m/s/219° Chilbulton report :- CB = 4500m OM CH (14.8kft) 2200m 20-30km - (7.280kft) pot 0 - 40km alt.
13:50.43	R7	FL110	76	51°0'/1°54'	669mb, -11.07°/-11.17° 19m/s/230°
13:54.48	R7	FL110	79	51°6'/1°24'	CH CH, 669mb -10.68°/-15.06° 14/218° huge amount pot except close to CH (see lat plot New) OK low 160cm ² , low SO ₂ , O ₃ , PCAST 20-30cm ² CAS 2cm ³

[CH] ↑

[SW] C

[CH] →

3 cycles from SW cut now ≡ 6 alt levels :-
+ return of those one = 7 levels

11000
10 hft
↑ hft
8 hft

7
6
5

CEN - 0.2% SO₂ cm²
CEN/CN = 1/3

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 433 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 8 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
[CH] → 13.59.59	R7E/P11	FL110	239	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH 669mb -10.81°/-13.76°C 23m/s/222° ppt starts 50km West CH
14.01.18	R1E/R8	FL100	253	51°6'/1°30'	695 mb -9.08°/-8.92°C, 31m/s/233 - bumps through after start - some water but ice denuded
14.04.43	RS	FL100	249	51°0'/1°46'	696 mb, -9.29°/-9.13° 29m/s/229 [Carbain. 232°/50kts]
					Chubb Update :- CB OH 3000m ↓ ppt at 16km range West CH
[SW] ↻ 14.15.56	R8E/PR	FL100	248	50°46'/2°42'	695 mb, -8.82°/-8.59°C 32m/s/228°
14.17.13	R12E/RA	FL90	22	50°54'/2°48'	723mb, -7.33°/-6.46°C 16m/s/210° CPI. Core Cloud - Snow and liquid water-droplets 15µm CPI - 50µm - <u>not</u> water, ice fragments
14.22.37	RA	FL90	80	50°54'/2°12'	723mb, -7.53°/-6.72°C 20m/s/222°
14.26.26	RA	FL90	81	51°0'/1°42'	723mb 7.86°C/-7.34° 20m/s/215 30Hz image 14.19. seen ppt at CH now 1000m - PCASP IS CDS - 2-3µm? 2DC 30/like FSSP - ~ 2-3µm? ← CDP - various
[CH] → 14.29.30	RA	FL90	80	51°6'/1°24'	(OH, CH) -7.51°/-7.73°, 19 m/s/217 723mb
14.31.02	RA	FL90	58	51°6'/1°12'	fanning 723mb -6.99°/-6.6°C 19m/s/223°

[-5.8 at 90 at 70, -5.8]
[-7.3 at 80 at 60, -4.3] planis legs.

CPI - ppt - dendrite over CH - ppt stopped now.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...433 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 9 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
(C4) 14.34.52	R9E/PB	FL90	241	51°6'/1°24'	723mb (OH CH), -7.73 / -7.81; 27/21°
					a pocket 200m wide - supercooled water
14.36.08	PB	FL80	252	51°6'/1°30'	750mb -6.51°/-6.59°C, 31mb / 222°
14.37.16	P13E/R10	FL70	245	51°6'/1°36'	781mb, -4.2°/-4.25°, 30m/s / 217°
					CPT - still no liquid water. !!
					MSc2 - CHiller high dead blunty cut
					CT (N: St) slopes up away from CH
					CT 3000m ~ 30km (9.8 km)
					4000m ~ 70km range (13.1 km)
					Circ dead - d CPT - seeing columns - don't
					slight heat water "not concrete"
14.44.43	R10	FL70	246	51°0'/2°6'	3mm snow flakes above us - gone completely
					(MSc2 - 4.5 km TWC - indications)
					Columns - both LW too - now gone
					both Columns dominating now.
					MSc2 - CH - Supercooled drops
					14 - 15 000 ft
					12 - 13,000 ft.
					CT - ~ constant 4000m ~ (13,000 ft)
14.51.03	R10	FL70	246	50°54'/2°30'	781mb -3.4°C/-3.00° 30m/s / 219ms
					[Cantaini = 52W / 226°]
					- current - columns much shorter than earlier
					- 2DS - 1000µm meter blob

P1P - 3mm particles seen now

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 433 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 10 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
14.52.38	R10 turn only	FL70			(Direct Flight. ETA Exeter 15.45) -3.1°/-3.54°C
14.55.56	R10E/P16	FL70	116	50°54'/2°30'	781mb, -3.51°/-3.34°C 26/218°
14.57.23	P14E/R11	FL60	81	50°54'/2°24'	810mb, -2.16°C/-1.85°C 26mbs/216° Turbulence Probe near bank (wind dir / speed seemed OK through)
					ODP - plenty spectra in ice - but.... water → mic spectra !!
					Been through cruise probe SC H2O now.
15.03.01	R11	FL60	82	51°0'/1°36'	Now all ice 811mb -2.7°/-2.4°C 16mbs/231°
15.06.15	R11	FL60	82	51°6'/1°24'	OH GA, 811mb -2.55°C/-2.31°C, 22/216
15.07.36	R11	FL60	80	51°6'/1°18'	Right turn at Peps 811mb, -2.81°/-2.21 21mbs/226°
					RMI - CT. now..... (step down).
					(Patland Reg 987 mb) (for bottom scrubtolls)
15.11.51	R11E/P15	FL60	246	51°6'/1°24'	811mb -2.31°/-2.47°C 32mbs/203
15.13.09	P15.1	4500 Alt	247	51°6'/1°30'	835/5.2kt 0.93°/-1.35° 29mbs/208°
15.14.27	P15.1	3500 Alt	238	51°0'/1°36'	867mb/4.2kt 0.01°/0.84° 27mbs/202°
15.15.02	P15.1/P15.2	3000 Alt	237	51°0'/1°36'	882/3.7kt 0.51°/1.95° 18/206°
15.16.53	P15.2/P15.3	5000 Alt	246	51°0'/1°48'	844/4.9kt -1.0°/0.19° 26/209°
15.18.01	P15.3	4000	244	51°0'/1°54'	874/4.0 0.34°/2.01° 18/207°
15.19.34	P15.3/P15.4	2500	246	51°0'/2°0'	918/2.6kt 3.2°/4.75° 23/210°
15.21.20	P15.4	4000	241	51°0'/2°6'	877/3.9kt 0.83°/2.45° 27/208°
15.22.17	P15.4 rev	4900	246	50°54'/2°12'	845/4.9kt -0.85°/0.31 27/209°
15.24.21	R12	FL50	244	50°54'/2°24'	843mb/4.9kt -0.38°/0.09° 31/212°
15.25.38	R12E/P16	FL50	242	50°54'/2°30'	843mb/ -0.74°/0.23° 31/210°
15.26.46	P16E/C13	FL40	244	50°54'/2°30'	872mb/ 1.0°/1.53° 30/212°
15.31.45	R13E	FL40	225	50°48'/2°54'	descent to Exeter approach. 877mb 1.46°/3.08 32/21°

(ground seen at 1000ft)
lots of rain on approach =

Landed. 15.42.10ish KNB (cross wind)
heavy prf (210/24kt) - gusting.

Cloud Physics Flight Log B433

Date: 03/03/09	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 09:38:00	DAU1 Time: Set	DAU2 Time: Set	DAU3 Time:N/A	AUX1 Time: Set	Aux2 Time: Set
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	PCASP		2DC		2DP		CDP		FFSSP		UMan FSSP		PIP	
Operated?	Y		Y		N		Y		Y		Y		Y	
Pre-flight checks	Vref (>3.5):	4.5	EI#1 V (>1):	-1.9	EI#1V:		Laser V(~3):	4.1	Ref V (~3):	3.5	Laser V (~9):	9.4	EI#1 V:	1.9
	Flow (~1):	0.79	EI#32 V (>1):	-1.6									EI #1V:	3.4
	Pressure:	993											EI#64 V:	2.4
	Temp (NDIT)	8.61												

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			Blocks Tx	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	
10:00																	CDP cleaned then calibrated with 40 and 10 micron beads.
11:05																	All heaters on
																	LWC Slave V = 0.65 LWC blown?
11:23:00	FL100	22	0.07	0					16	0.1	6	0		0			Start P1
11:24:09	FL090	22	0.07	0					16	0.05	3	0		0			
11:25:09	FL080	32	0.07	0					16	0.05	3	0		0			
11:26:00	FL070	421	0.22	62	500			1	69	140	28	11	24	0.006	4500		
11:27:00	FL060	60	0.33	34	225			1	173	140	23	10	18	0.006	3000		
11:29:30	FL060	237	0.27	80	625			1	302	80	20	80	20	0.002	1000		
11:30:25	FL050	67	0.08	7	500			1	313	20	40	0		0.004	2000		
11:31:24	FL040	52	0.13	6	450			1	328	160	8	150	10	0.001	20		
11:33:30	FL040	28	0.25	2	250			1	388	125	20	100	18	0			
11:35:20	FL030	86	0.15	0					454	100	12	200	12	0			
11:41:30	FL020	290	0.06	0					778	0		0		0			
11:42:22	FL015	244	0.06	0					779	0		0		0			
11:43:09	FL010	250	0.06	0					779	0		0		0			
11:43:53	50FT	125	0.07	0					779	0		0		0			END P2 BOSC DOWN
11:45:10	FL020	102	0.07	0					779	0		0		0			
11:45:40	FL030	91	0L14	5	250			1	815	300	18			0.002	1500		
11:46:45	FL050	37	0.16	14	175			1	917	300	22			0.001	200		

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			Blocks Tx	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	
11:48:20	FL070	1	0.08	0					1096	0		0		0			
11:49:45	FL090	17	0.08	0					1096	0		0		0			
11:50:50	FL100	25	0.07	0					1096	0		0		0			
11:51:30	FL110	6	0.06	0					1096	0		0		0			
11:52:15	FL120	2	0.07	0					1096	0		0		0			
11:53:03	FL130	16	0.07	0					1096	0		0		0			
11:54:00	FL150	20	0.14	40	600			8,4	1097	0		0		0.012	3000		
11:55:33	FL160	3	0.55	70	775			8	1100	NOISE		?		0.025	4000		
11:56:28	FL170	3	0.15	50	425			8	1101	NOISE		?		0.015	3000		
11:57:10	FL180	0	0.40	56	450			8	1102	NOISE		?		0.02	2000		
11:58:04	FL190	4	0.20	62	450			8,4	1103	NOISE		?		0.03	4200		
11:58:57	FL200	34	0.10	60	525			8,4	1105	NOISE		?		0.03	3200		
11:59:50	FL210	5	0.07	29	275			11	1106	NOISE		?		0.005	0		
12:00:50	FL220	6	0.07	42	200			11	1106	NOISE		0		0.005	0		
12:01:39	FL230	10	0.18	81	400			11,4	1107	NOISE		0		0.03	2000		
12:03:04	FL240	5	0.09	0					1108	NOISE		0		0			
12:04:30	FL250	12	0.08	0					1108	0		0		0			
12:05:57	FL260	15	0.12	15	275			11	1109	NOISE		0		0.03	1500		
12:07:54	FL270	26	0.41	80	175			11	1112	NOISE		0		0.001	0		END PROFILE 3
12:08:40	FL260	16	0.06	12	175			11	1112	NOISE		0		0.001	0		
12:09:32	FL250	18	0.24	145	300			11	1113	NOISE		0		0.005	0		
12:10:33	FL240	20	0.20	61	225			11	1113	NOISE		0		0.01	1000		
12:11:32	FL230	16	0.23	94	225			11	1115	NOISE		0		0.03	150		END P4 START R1
12:15:00	FL230	15	0.22	107	425			11,8	1118	NOISE		0		0.05	100		CPI SEEING ROSETTES
12:18:00	FL230	20	0.10	1	250			11	1119	0		0		0			
12:19:40	FL230	15	0.10	80	175			11	1121	NOISE		NOIS		0			CBOLTON
12:22:00	FL230	15	0.13	114	225			11,8	1123	NOISE		NOIS		0.003	100		
12:23:00	FL230	13	0.06	41	150			11	1125	NOISE				0			
12:25:00	FL230	2	0.08	34	175			11	1128	NOISE		NOIS		0			CBOLTON START P5
12:25:59	FL220	8	0.08	0					1128	0		0		0			
12:27:00	FL210	11	0.08	0					1128	0		0		0			END P5 START R2
12:28:30	FL210	6	0.08	31	275			11,8	1129	0		0		0.002	0		
12:30:30	FL210	3	0.07	15	200			8,11	1129	0		0		0			
12:32:00	FL210	12	0.31	131	325			8	1131	NOISE		0		0.045	200		
12:34:00	FL210	13	0.13	34	350			8	1135	NOISE		NOIS		0.01	0		
12:37:00	FL210	11	0.14	113	350			8,4	1139	NOISE		NOIS		0.03	2500		END R2 START P6
12:38:29	FL200	9	0.64	86	500			8,4	1145	NOISE		NOIS		0.05	3500		

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	LWC	
12:39:29	FL190	13	0.36	86	550			8	1147	NOISE				0.03	2000		
12:42:20	FL190	3	1.00	31	500			8,4,5	1154	NOISE				0.01	200		
12:44:00	FL190	8	0.15	40	425			8,4	1157	NOISE				0.03	4000		
12:48:00	FL190	10	0.12	41	175			11	1161	NOISE		3	28	0.02	100		
12:49:36	FL190	2	0.07	0					1163	0		0		0			CBOLTON
12:53:00	FL190	5	0.06	3	450			8	1164	0		0		0			
12:55:00	FL190	11	0.07	78	300			8	1165	NOISE		4	28	0.005	0		
12:56:24	FL180	3	0.06	23	250			8	1166	NOISE		1	25	0.005	0		
12:57:31	FL170	30	0.11	24	500			8,4,5	1166	NOISE		2	30	0.005	400		END P START R
12:59:00	FL170	13	0.49	75	575			8,4	1170	NOISE		4	30	0.01	300		
13:01:00	FL170	21	0.11	40	650			8, 12?	1174	NOISE		8	30	0.015	400		
13:03:00	FL170	10	0.54	107	475			8,11/12?	1182	NOISE		7	30	0.025	300		
13:05:00	FL170	11	0.28	103	675			8,11/12, 4	1189	NOISE		5	30	0.02	300		
13:07:00	FL170	13	0.47	106	700			8,11/12	1196	NOISE		8	30	0.018	1000		
13:11:30	FL170	6	0.38	75	750			8,4,11,12	1209	NOISE		8	30	0.01	400		
13:13:39	FL150	63	0.41	109	675			8,11	1220	NOISE		10	30	0.02	400		
13:16:30	FL150	31	0.25	109	675			8,11,12	1231	NOISE		8	30	0.02	400		
13:19:00	FL150	22	0.10	67	500			8	1238	NOISE		4	32	0.01	200		
13:21:22	FL150	13	0.08	0					1239	NOISE		0		0			CBOLTON
13:27:50	FL140	26	0.12	0					1239	NOISE		0		0			PROFILE 9
13:28:54	FL130	21	0.08	0					1239	NOISE		0		0			START R6
13:32:00	FL130	17	0.07	65	575			8,12	1247	NOISE		14	31	0.02	570		
13:34:17	FL130	8	0.38	68	750			8,12	1255	NOISE		8	31	0.02	500		
13:37:13	FL130	1	0.21	45	800			8,4,12	1266	NOISE		8	32	0.01	700		
13:40:14	FL130	1	0.94	19	800			8,12	1271	NOISE		3	32	0.004	375		
13:43:57	FL110	10	0.23	50	800			8,12	1276	NOISE		3	32	0.004	1000		
13:47:04	FL110	15	0.25	65	675			8,11,12	1280	NOISE		5	32	0.01	900		
12:50:00	FL110	12	0.26	60	725			8,11,12	1289	NOISE		4	32	0.01	760		
13:52:25	FL110	22	0.15	23	625			8,11,12	1296	NOISE		2	31	0.02	450		
13:54:07	FL110	7	0.07	0					1299	0		0		0			
13:54:51	FL110	19	0.07	0					1299	0		0		0			CBOLTON
13:58:06	FL110	14	0.08	0					1299	0		0		0			
14:00:09	FL110	2	0.33	3	725			8,4	1300			10	32	0.01	622		START PROFILE 11
14:01:21	FL100	1	0.08	2	725			8,4,5,11	1302			2	38	0.01	660		START RUN 8
14:03:03	FL100	30	0.47	50	775			8,4,11,12	1308			3	32	0.01	1200		
14:06:02	FL100	10	0.44	55	725			8,4,11,12	1314			3	32	0.01	800		
14:08:55	FL100	3	0.14	18	625			8,11,12	1317	NOISE		2	31	0.005	650		

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	LWC	
14:12:02	FL100	11	0.44	80	725			8,9,11,12	1326	NOISE		5	32	0.01	980		
14:15:01	FL100	17	0.21	77	800			8,9,11,12	1339	NOISE		5	32	0.01	1500		
14:16:01	FL100	12	0.23	38	725			8,9,11,12	1343	NOISE		5	33	0.01	3500		
14:17:16	FL090	7	0.23	50	725			8,9,12	1350	NOISE		20	28	0.01	2200		
14:20:14	FL090	17	0.22	50	750			8,9,12	1367	NOISE		12	28	0.01	2500		
14:22:36	FL090	24	0.19	53	800			9,8,12,1	1379	NOISE		5	32	0.002	1700		
14:26:10	FL090	18	0.15	37	800			8,4,11,12	1385	NOISE		2	30	0.002	1000		
14:29:09	FL090	7	0.34	24	800			8,11,12	1388	NOISE		2	32	0.004	890		
14:33:04	FL090	17	0.24	30	800			8,9,11,12	1391	NOISE		2	32	0.004	960		
14:34:56	FL090	13	0.10	19	650			8,9,11,12	1394	NOISE		2	32	0.004	1030		
14:36:12	FL080	21	0.16	31	725			8,11,12	1399	NOISE		2	32	0.004	1300		
14:37:20	FL070	7	0.31	26	775			8,9,11,1	1401	NOISE		2	32	0.004	1400		
14:39:09	FL070	9	0.06	26	675			8,4,11	1405	NOISE		3	33	0.003	4700		
14:42:02	FL070	3	0.36	63	800			8,9,11,12	1413	NOISE		3	34	0.01	4000		
14:43:42	FL070	20	0.34	145	775			5,8,11,12	1423	NOISE		5	32	0.02	4000		
14:44:58	FL070	13	0.19	69	775			5,9,8	1432	NOISE		8	31	0.05	4500		
14:47:12	FL070	15	0.31	163	800			5,9,11,12	1457	NOISE		8	33	0.02	3500		
14:50:01	FL070	7	0.31	120	700			5,9,11,12	1477	NOISE		5	32	0.01	2000		
14:53:01	FL070	3	0.19	75	725			5,8	1485	NOISE		2	31	0.01	400		COLUMNS SHORTER
14:57:25	FL060	13	0.09	114	800			8,9,11,12	1503	12	20	4	32	0.01	3000		END P10 START R15
15:00:19	FL060	3	0.29	213	650			8,5,11	1539	NOISE		5	32	0.01	2200		
15:03:48	FL060	8	0.21	92	775			8,5,11	1555	NOISE		5	32	0.01	1600		
15:07:44	FL060	2	0.37	49	600			8,11,12	1570	20	20	20	28	0.005	1800		
15:10:33	FL060	4	0.17	45	675			8,11,12	1581	1	5	5	32	0.005	1500		
15:13:28	FL050	5	0.28	60	800			8,5,9,12,1	1609	20	33	35	25	0.01	3500		TURBULENCE
15:14:54	FL040	32	0.14	10	800			1,12	1764	97	20	100	20	0.005	2500		
15:16:57	FL050	109	0.26	40	775			1,8	1848	39	21	30	28	0.005	3000		
15:17:59	FL040	40	0.20	13	775			1,8	1916	130	17	100	18	0.005	800		SAWTOOTHES
15:19:22	FL030	108	0.22	6	800			1,12	2039	200	11	150	15	0.005	1200		
15:21:36	FL040	71	0.21	2	800			1,8,9	2199	115	22	100	20	0.005	1800		
15:22:25	FL050	46	0.21	100	800			1,9,8	2227	40	22	30	22	0.01	1600		
15:25:42	FL050	32	0.35	53	675			1,8	2277	12	17	20	20	0.01	1000		
15:26:47	FL040	75	0.27	22	675			1,11	2314	72	22	100	25	0.01	500		START RUN
15:29:00	FL040	160	0.22	28	350			1	2402	80	25	80	25	0.005	400		
15:41																	HEATERS OFF LAND EXETER

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	LWC	

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP	Vref:	4.2	OK
	Flow:	0.8	
2DC	EI#1:		OK
	EI#32:		
2DP	EI#1:		NOT FITTED
FFSSP	Ref V:		HARD TO TELL. SEEMED OK
CDP	Laser V:		Noise in ice cloud. Good otherwise
UMan FSSP	Laser V:		SEEMED OK.
PIP	EI#1:		MVDs distorted by v small numbers of v large particles. Good data. Possible LWC sensor problem.
	EI#32:		
	EI#64:		
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining. 1GB remaining.

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B433
Date of flight: 03/03/09

T/O: 11:
Land: 15:42:05

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown (see comment box) e) End time: 240000 if unknown		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> JW LWC para 535 Nevzorov LWC para 602 FFSSP LWC para 1202 ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B433
Date of Flight: 03/03/09

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	61290 BLOCKS
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 30621
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 58456 Blocks written = 58456 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y Y	Start = 110000 End = 154500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Only 2DC operated Images good. Mainly ice/mixed phase Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 110000, 133000 End = 133000, 154500 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions 2 files merged 71 pages + 105 pages

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	<p>8</p> <p>N/A</p>	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful. X = b433_tas</p> <p>Start = 110000 End = 154500</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records = 20594</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>X = b433_tas Y = (X+1) = b433_tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B433
Date of Flight: 03/03/09

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y 1 0.79	 Min size = Vol flow rate =
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_proccasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_proccasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proccasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas_2d Y = X+1 = _tas_2d_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Y Use flight_plot to check.

Flight:

B433

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B433
Date: 03/03/09

Instruments

1. Horace being a pain, this time insertion of the disk sorted the problem!
2. Neph has a problem, rubbish data, stable but very high like 40000m-1
3. 11:50 turbulence probe iced, lost angle of attack back at 14:52 (-2.6C)
4. Horace died again on landing No data recorded since 15:43 ish

Issues

latestVEL_03032009_1112h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1136h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1201h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1208h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1224h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1227h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1237h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1243h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1306h.png

3-GHz radar

Tuesday 3 Mar 2009 13:15:47 RHI 8007/222 Azim 255.0°

latestVEL_03032009_1315h.png

3-GHz radar

Tuesday 3 Mar 2009 13:22:05 RHI 8007/224 Azim 255.0°

latestVEL_03032009_1322h.png

3-GHz radar

Tuesday 3 Mar 2009 13:31:31 RHI 8007/227 Azim 255.0°

latestVEL_03032009_1331h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1337h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1402h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1414h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1419h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1420h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1431h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1433h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1454h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1459h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1505h.png

latestVEL_03032009_1519h.png

~P1 start

Into cloud - bumpy

Hold at 6000ftl

Resume P1

Local CB

P1 hold at 4000ft

P2 start QFE 991mb to 2000

Alt 2500ft

2000ft

RT at 2000ft

P2 resume

1500ft

1000ft

500ft

50ft

500ft

1000ft

2000ft

CB 2200ft

3500ft

4100ft

5100ft

6000ft

CT

FL100 1013mb

FL110

CB's very thin – CPI seeing ice

FL151

FL165

RHT

FL225

FL230

1st CT at FL240

FL250

FL260

Local CT

End P3 start P4

FL255

End P4 start R1

Above CT locally

R1 OH CH

R1 end start P5 OH CH

End P5 start R2

End R2 start P6

FL200

End P6, start R3 FL190

OH CH

OH CH

End R3 start P7 FL190

End P7 start R4 CPI mode size inc

Turning R4 SW end

End R4 start P8

New plot, same times

Flight B433 13:12:40
Heading 100 deg Speed 280 knots Height 15.9kft Press 550mb
Lat 50°54.0'N Long 2°30.0'W Wind 14 ms-1/222 deg
Temp -21.77C Dewpoint -20.75C
From 11:10:00 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 47559 secs All sc
PRESSURE HEIGHT 15.95 Kft

Flight B433 13:13:07
Heading 87 deg Speed 287 knots Height 15.4kft Press 560mb
Lat 50°54.0'N Long 2°24.0'W Wind 13 ms-1/214 deg
Temp -20.77C Dewpoint -21.07C
From 11:10:00 to now

Current values
STATIC PRESSURE 560.49 mb
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -20.77 deg C
DEW POINT -21.07 deg C

End P8 start R5

Bumpy as going E

OH CH

turning

End R5 start P9 OH CH

End P9 start R6

CC and CPI report water

End R6 start P10

FL119

End P10 start R7

Flight Summary B433

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
ASP	10:57:44	172	0.59kft	52.1N	0.6W						open
T/O	11:02:54	211	0.00kft	52.1N	0.6W						
note	11:26:00	190	7.1kft	51.8N	1.7W						horace drop out problems
Profile 2	11:34:35	172	3.9kft	51.4N	1.5W	11:43:52	228	0.66kft	51.2N	1.7W	missed approach to boscombe
Profile 3	11:45:41	255	3.1kft	51.1N	1.8W	12:07:50	245	27.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	11:43ish check
Profile 4	12:07:50	245	27.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	12:11:32	111	23.1kft	51.0N	2.6W	
Run 1	12:11:33	110	23.1kft	51.0N	2.6W	12:25:01	251	23.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	ontop CHBolt
note	12:20:05	061	23.0kft	51.2N	1.4W						11:19:40 chilbolton ontop
Profile 5	12:25:01	251	23.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	12:27:10	252	21.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	ontop CHBolt
Run 2	12:27:11	252	21.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	12:37:32	253	21.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 6	12:37:32	253	21.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	12:39:27	078	19.0kft	51.0N	2.8W	
Run 3	12:39:27	078	19.0kft	51.0N	2.8W	12:55:15	247	19.1kft	51.1N	1.5W	
Note	12:49:37	077	19.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						on top chilbolton
notye	12:54:56	243	19.1kft	51.1N	1.4W						chil
Profile 7	12:55:16	247	19.1kft	51.1N	1.5W	12:57:31	249	17.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Run 4	12:57:31	249	17.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	13:11:40	116	17.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	
Profile 8	13:11:40	116	17.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	13:13:38	078	15.1kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Run 4	13:13:39	078	15.0kft	51.0N	2.4W	13:26:39	241	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	overhead CHilB actually run 5
note	13:21:21	078	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						OH ChBol
note	13:25:02	282	15.0kft	51.2N	1.3W						waters caled
Profile 9	13:26:40	241	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	13:28:55	251	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	overhead CHilB actually run 5
Run 6	13:28:55	251	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	13:41:46	250	12.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	

Flight B433 13:52:44
Heading 79 deg Speed 241 knots Height 11.0kft Press 669mb
Lat 51°0.0'N Long 1°36.0'W Wind 19 ms-1/ 226 deg
Temp -10.9C Dewpoint -12.02C
From 12:10:00 to now

Current values

—	GIN LONGITUDE	-1.69	deg (+ve E)	☒	All
—	JW LIQUID WATER CONTENT	0.01	g m-3	☐	
—	NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0.03	g m-3	☐	
—	NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	0	g m-3	☐	

OH CH

OH CH end R7 start P11

End P11 start R8

New plot, same times

Flight B433 14:08:20
Heading 248 deg Speed 228 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb
Lat 51°0.0'N Long 2°6.0'W Wind 28 ms-1/ 227 deg
Temp -9.07C Dewpoint -9.08C
From 12:10:00 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	50898	secs	☒	All	☒	sc
—	JW LIQUID WATER CONTENT	0.02	g m-3	☐			
—	NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0.04	g m-3	☐			
—	NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	0.05	g m-3	☐			

Profile 2	11:34:35	172	3.9kft	51.4N	1.5W	11:43:52	228	0.66kft	51.2N	1.7W	missed approach to boscombe
Profile 3	11:45:41	255	3.1kft	51.1N	1.8W	12:07:50	245	27.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	11:43ish check
Profile 4	12:07:50	245	27.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	12:11:32	111	23.1kft	51.0N	2.6W	
Run 1	12:11:33	110	23.1kft	51.0N	2.6W	12:25:01	251	23.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	ontop CHBolt
note	12:20:05	061	23.0kft	51.2N	1.4W						11:19:40 chilbolton ontop
Profile 5	12:25:01	251	23.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	12:27:10	252	21.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	ontop CHBolt
Run 2	12:27:11	252	21.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	12:37:32	253	21.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 6	12:37:32	253	21.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	12:39:27	078	19.0kft	51.0N	2.8W	
Run 3	12:39:27	078	19.0kft	51.0N	2.8W	12:55:15	247	19.1kft	51.1N	1.5W	
Note	12:49:37	077	19.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						on top chilbolton
notye	12:54:56	243	19.1kft	51.1N	1.4W						chil
Profile 7	12:55:16	247	19.1kft	51.1N	1.5W	12:57:31	249	17.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Run 4	12:57:31	249	17.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	13:11:40	116	17.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	
Profile 8	13:11:40	116	17.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	13:13:38	078	15.1kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Run 4	13:13:39	078	15.0kft	51.0N	2.4W	13:26:39	241	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	overhead CHilB actually run 5
note	13:21:21	078	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						OH ChBol
note	13:25:02	282	15.0kft	51.2N	1.3W						waters caled
Profile 9	13:26:40	241	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	13:28:55	251	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	overhead CHilB actually run 5
Run 6	13:28:55	251	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	13:41:46	250	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 10	13:41:46	250	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	13:43:58	106	11.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	
Run 7	13:43:58	106	11.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	14:00:01	239	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	oh chil b
note	13:54:47	079	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						OH CHilB
Profile 11	14:00:01	239	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	14:01:20	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	oh chil b
Run 8	14:01:20	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.6W						

End R8 start P12

End P12 start R9

OH CH inbound R9

turning

End R9 start P13 OH CH

End P13 start R10

Just seeing columns dominating now 5mm snow

Turn - no descent R10

End R10 start P14

End P14 start R11 inbound

OH CH

RT Pepis recip

End R11 start P15.1

P15.1 4500ft

P15.1 3500ft

End P15.1 at 3000ft start P15.2 bumpy end P15.2 at 5000ft start P15.3

P15.3 at 4000ft

end P15.3 at 2500ft start P15.4

P15.4 at 4000ft

End P15.4 at 5000ft maintaining alt

Maintaining FL50

End R12 start P16

End P16 start R13

note	13:25:02	282	15.0kft	51.2N	1.3W							waters caled
Profile 9	13:26:40	241	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	13:28:55	251	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W		overhead CHilB actually run 5
Run 6	13:28:55	251	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	13:41:46	250	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W		
Profile 10	13:41:46	250	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	13:43:58	106	11.0kft	51.0N	2.7W		
Run 7	13:43:58	106	11.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	14:00:01	239	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W		oh chil b
note	13:54:47	079	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W							OH CHilB
Profile 11	14:00:01	239	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	14:01:20	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.6W		oh chil b
Run 8	14:01:20	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	14:16:00	248	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W		
Profile 12	14:16:00	248	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	14:17:13	022	9.0kft	50.9N	2.8W		
Run 9	14:17:14	022	9.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	14:34:58	241	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W		oh chilB
note	14:29:31	080	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W							oh cHILb
Profile 13	14:34:58	241	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	14:37:18	245	7.0kft	51.1N	1.6W		oh chilB
Run 10	14:37:19	245	7.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	14:55:56	116	7.0kft	51.0N	2.6W		
Profile 14	14:55:56	116	7.0kft	51.0N	2.6W	14:57:23	081	6.0kft	51.0N	2.4W		
Run 11	14:57:24	081	6.0kft	51.0N	2.4W	15:11:51	246	6.0kft	51.1N	1.5W		OH CHilB
note	15:06:15	082	6.0kft	51.1N	1.4W							OH CHilB-ton
Profile 15.1	15:11:51	246	6.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	15:15:05	238	3.8kft	51.1N	1.7W		OH CHilB
Profile 15.2	15:15:05	238	3.8kft	51.1N	1.7W	15:16:57	246	4.9kft	51.1N	1.9W		
Profile 15.3	15:16:58	246	4.9kft	51.1N	1.9W	15:19:38	246	2.6kft	51.0N	2.1W		
Profile 15.4	15:19:39	245	2.6kft	51.0N	2.1W	15:22:18	247	4.9kft	51.0N	2.3W		
Profile 15.5	15:22:18	247	4.9kft	51.0N	2.3W	15:22:49	248	5.0kft	51.0N	2.3W		
Run 12	15:23:05	244	5.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	15:25:40	242	5.0kft	50.9N	2.5W		started at end of 15.5
Profile 16	15:25:40	242	5.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	15:26:47	244	4.0kft	50.9N	2.6W		started at end of 15.5
Run 13	15:26:47	244	4.0kft	50.9N	2.6W							

End R13 start descent

note	13:25:02	282	15.0kft	51.2N	1.3W							waters caled
Profile 9	13:26:40	241	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	13:28:55	251	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W		overhead CHilB actually run 5
Run 6	13:28:55	251	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	13:41:46	250	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W		
Profile 10	13:41:46	250	13.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	13:43:58	106	11.0kft	51.0N	2.7W		
Run 7	13:43:58	106	11.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	14:00:01	239	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W		oh chil b
note	13:54:47	079	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W							OH CHilB
Profile 11	14:00:01	239	11.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	14:01:20	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.6W		oh chil b
Run 8	14:01:20	253	10.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	14:16:00	248	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W		
Profile 12	14:16:00	248	10.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	14:17:13	022	9.0kft	50.9N	2.8W		
Run 9	14:17:14	022	9.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	14:34:58	241	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W		oh chilB
note	14:29:31	080	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W							oh cHILb
Profile 13	14:34:58	241	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	14:37:18	245	7.0kft	51.1N	1.6W		oh chilB
Run 10	14:37:19	245	7.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	14:55:56	116	7.0kft	51.0N	2.6W		
Profile 14	14:55:56	116	7.0kft	51.0N	2.6W	14:57:23	081	6.0kft	51.0N	2.4W		
Run 11	14:57:24	081	6.0kft	51.0N	2.4W	15:11:51	246	6.0kft	51.1N	1.5W		OH CHilB
note	15:06:15	082	6.0kft	51.1N	1.4W							OH CHilB-ton
Profile 15.1	15:11:51	246	6.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	15:15:05	238	3.8kft	51.1N	1.7W		OH CHilB
Profile 15.2	15:15:05	238	3.8kft	51.1N	1.7W	15:16:57	246	4.9kft	51.1N	1.9W		
Profile 15.3	15:16:58	246	4.9kft	51.1N	1.9W	15:19:38	246	2.6kft	51.0N	2.1W		
Profile 15.4	15:19:39	245	2.6kft	51.0N	2.1W	15:22:18	247	4.9kft	51.0N	2.3W		
Profile 15.5	15:22:18	247	4.9kft	51.0N	2.3W	15:22:49	248	5.0kft	51.0N	2.3W		
Run 12	15:23:05	244	5.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	15:25:40	242	5.0kft	50.9N	2.5W		started at end of 15.5
Profile 16	15:25:40	242	5.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	15:26:47	244	4.0kft	50.9N	2.6W		started at end of 15.5
Run 13	15:26:47	244	4.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	15:31:45	225	4.0kft	50.8N	2.9W		

New plot, same times

Flight B433 15:32:57
Heading 235 deg Speed 201 knots Height 3.1kft Press 904mb
Lat 50°48.0'N Long 2°54.0'W Wind 34 ms-1/ 208 deg
Temp 3.19C Dewpoint 4.45C
From 11:10:00 to now

Current values
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 55977 secs All sc
PRESSURE HEIGHT 3.12 Kft